

LOW-FREQUENCY EIS INTERCEPT AS A DIAGNOSTIC TOOL FOR PEM FUEL CELLS DEGRADATION

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Abstract - Several diagnostic tests, such as polarization curves, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), and cyclic voltammetry (CV), were conducted periodically to monitor performance degradation during an accelerated stress test (AST) for catalyst degradation on a single proton exchange membrane (PEM) fuel cell, which involves voltage cycling. From the results of the EIS measurements taken during the AST at three different current densities, catalyst degradation is clearly shown. The low-frequency intercept (Total R) increased most significantly. The simulation results with an 11-element impedance model show very good agreement with experimental data and consistency with the polarization change curves and CV. The obtained impedance at Total R is purely real, and it can be a useful and perhaps sufficient indicator for catalyst degradation and determination of the cell current state from just one parameter value, which is very promising for the future implementation in the PEM fuel cell control system.

Index Terms - catalyst degradation; accelerated stress test; electrochemical impedance spectroscopy; low-frequency intercept

I. ACCELERATED DEGRADATION TESTS AND DIAGNOSTICS

In this paper, the applicability of the low-frequency intercept in the impedance spectrum was preliminary investigated during an accelerated stress test (AST) as a diagnostic tool for catalyst degradation performed on a water-cooled single proton exchange membrane (PEM) fuel cell hardware in a co-flow configuration from ElringKlinger with a 50 cm^2 active area MEA. Several diagnostic techniques, such as polarization curves, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and cyclic voltammetry (CV) were conducted periodically to monitor performance degradation during the AST. The cell has been subjected to the AST designed to target electrocatalyst degradation, which involves 40 s long potential cycling profile with rest times of 10 s at 0.6 V and 30 s at 0.9 V with 1 V s^{-1} voltage ramps. The voltage was imposed on the cell at 65°C and 0.5 bar(g) via an external instrument (BioLogic SP-150) as the

cell was in a non-operating mode, i.e. nitrogen was used on the cathode and hydrogen on the anode side with constant flows of 0.4 SLPM and inlet relative humidities (RH) of 100% (dew point of 65°C). A Scribner Associates 890CL Teledyne Medusa fuel cell test station with an electronic load and a frequency response analyzer was used for the experiments, especially EIS measurements, which were conducted in galvanostatic mode in the frequency range from 3.981 kHz to 10 mHz with AC signal amplitude of 10% of the DC current. Each scan took around 30 minutes with additional 5 minutes of stabilization phase prior to each testing. Comparison of EIS measurements at 0.3, 0.6 and 1.2 A cm^{-2} is shown in Fig. 1 at the beginning of life (BoL) and after 5000 cycles on a degrading hydrogen/air fuel cell operated at 65°C and 0.5 bar(g), with reactants inlet RH of 83.4% (dew point of 61°C) and constant stoichiometry of 4.0/2.0.

Fig. 1. Nyquist plots at different current densities at the BoL and after 5000 cycles of AST

From the results of the EIS measurements taken during the AST, catalyst degradation is clearly shown. The semicircles' high-frequency branches are more tilted/distorted with degradation, indicating an increase in the catalyst layer (CL) ionic resistance, while the low-frequency loops, representing

mass transport losses, are getting bigger. As a result, the rightmost real-axis intercept on the Nyquist diagram around 0.5 Hz or lower (maximum real impedance and the highest resistive losses), increased most significantly, while the membrane resistance (the leftmost real-axis intercept at high frequencies) increased only slightly. Obviously, there is a mixture of increase in activation losses (related to the loss of the cathode electrochemical active surface area, ECSA) and mass transport losses. This concurs also with the findings (at least qualitatively) of the polarization change curves analysis and CV measurements, which indicated a slight loss of the ECSA caused by platinum dissolution due to intentional frequent voltage cycling. The loss of the ECSA apparently resulted in slight structural changes within the CL, as the slight increase in mass transport suggests.

II. APPLICATION OF MODEL TO FUEL CELL DEGRADATION STUDY

In the authors' recently published paper [1], an 11-element impedance model of PEM fuel cell was developed as a modified Randles equivalent circuit, capable of capturing the processes that cause the low-frequency inductive loop in the impedance spectra. It was validated by a series of experiments varying the operating conditions. Here, it has been applied on the periodical impedance measurements at the BoL, after 1000, 3000 and 5000 cycles to monitor performance degradation during the AST at three different current densities, and simulation results show very good agreement with the experiments. An example of model fitting results compared with experimental data at 0.6 A cm^{-2} during the AST is given in the Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Comparison of measured and simulated impedance spectra at 0.6 A cm^{-2} during the AST

The low-frequency intercept is the sum of all model resistors [1] and it shows a rising trend during the AST at every measured current density (Fig. 3). Their overall values in the same point of AST are lower at higher current densities, and their rising trends are similar at all current densities.

Fig. 3. Comparison of low-frequency intercepts at different current densities during the AST

III. CONCLUSION

The observed single PEM fuel cell moderately degraded during the AST after 5000 voltage cycles. The catalyst degradation was diagnosed with periodical EIS measurements taken during the AST at three different current densities. The low-frequency intercept increased most significant during the AST, with a rising and similar trend at every measured current density, whereas the membrane resistance increased only slightly. This concurs also with the findings of the polarization change curves analysis and CV measurements, which indicated a slight loss of the ECSA caused by platinum dissolution due to intentionally frequent voltage cycling. The loss of the ECSA apparently resulted in slight structural changes within the CL, as the slight increase in mass transport suggests.

As the obtained impedance at the low-frequency intercept is purely real and shows the most significant change with degradation, it can be a useful and perhaps sufficient indicator for catalyst degradation. Therefore, the new on-line algorithm for direct impedance estimation, based on relay excitation feedback, will find the appropriate frequency and calculate the impedance. The algorithm establishes a stable limit cycle oscillation with specified small amplitude and will converge quite fast to the frequency with the desired phase properties of the impedance. The algorithm can be implemented in ordinary fuel-cell control systems. Thus, catalyst degradation can be monitored without the need of measuring the whole impedance spectrum, and it will determine the current state of the fuel cell from just one parameter value, which is very promising for the future implementation in the fuel cell control system. The direct identification approach will be further explored.

REFERENCES

- [1] Pivac, I., Šimić, B., Barbir, F., Experimental diagnostics and modeling of inductive phenomena at low frequencies in impedance spectra of proton exchange membrane fuel cells, *Journal of Power Sources*, Vol. 365, 2017, pp. 240-248.